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Annotation: Today, distance learning has entered the educational system as a convenient and unique type of education. Distance education is a form of obtaining information in which, in addition to full-time and part-time education, traditional and innovative methods, tools and forms of education based on computer and telecommunication technologies are widely used. In the distance education tool, a controlled educational process focused on one goal is organized using special opportunities, telephone, electronic communication and other educational tools based on an individual schedule in a place convenient for the student. This article focuses on the specific features and advantages of distance education.

Keywords: distance learning, tools, e-mail address, learning process, knowledge, freedom, efficiency, audio-video, animation, graphics.

Introduction: It aims to change educational standards in modern education, which is developing at a fast pace today, to raise the quality of education, and to increase the efficiency of educational processes. This requires the higher education institution to make strong efforts to adapt to rapidly changing conditions and to meet new requirements for the educational process. The future of higher education, the training of a modern type of specialist, implies increasing the activity and responsibility of both teachers and students. Alternatively, some established models and concepts of pragmatic meaning lose their value. At this point, most universities should take on the task of reinventing and creating sustainable models that can engage students in a specific educational process that opens up new opportunities for them with increasing innovative efforts.

Revolutionary changes in information technologies naturally increase the importance of teachers' active use of multimedia tools in the process of forming a new educational environment, which is the basis for improving the quality of modern education. With the help of interactive technologies, students will have the opportunity not only to learn the material of lectures and seminars at a high level through visual perception, but also to work with a large amount of information and develop information culture. At this point, it is worth noting that the majority of professors and teachers of higher education institutions use technical tools and innovative computer technologies in their pedagogical activities in the process of organizing lectures and seminar courses. Teachers who do not use technical tools and innovative computer technologies almost do not exist in the education system today. After all, modern information technologies have now become a tool used by all representatives of the educational sector to organize teaching processes meaningfully.

Studying the opinions of students and teachers about the impact of innovative computer teaching technologies on the process of assimilation of lecture and seminar material will serve to create good news for the use of information technologies in the classroom. Almost one in two teachers and students believe that the use of computer technologies significantly facilitates the understanding and mastering of the material. At the same time, more than half of teachers and students believe that the use of innovations and innovative technologies partially facilitates the educational process. Multimedia presentation systems are the most common technical tools used

by most teachers, who are active participants in today's fast-paced modern educational environment. If a questionnaire or a similar practical process is conducted among professors and teachers on this very issue, without a doubt, it is clear that many of them emphasize that they often use multimedia in the organization of lectures and seminar courses.

It should be said that innovative teaching methods (mainly presentations with explanatory materials) are often active in the organization of lesson processes by lecturers. About half of the professors use this type of presentation, and among the associate professors - the absolute majority.

While the teacher in charge of the lesson processes organizes a lesson based on innovative pedagogical technologies, efficient use of various technical means - computer, projector, electronic whiteboard, etc., and the application of interactive methods in more lesson processes also serve for the effectiveness of the educational process. If a teacher of any category who knows how to use innovative pedagogical technologies and interactive methods in education has a large number of practices in their use, it is possible to observe an increase in the content of the lessons. In addition, each teacher can introduce innovations in education individually. Studying and summarizing theoretical and practical information about the content and topics of the science for which he is responsible, the advanced achievements and innovations of science created in this field, teaching being able to use them appropriately in their processes, creating new methods in education and organizing lesson processes on the basis of these will also serve to enrich the content of the lesson.

Great attention is paid to the development of distance education in our country. Many people think that distance education is just a new form of correspondence education as we know it. To a certain extent, this is true: in reality, a person can study without leaving his home. But there is one condition: for this, you must have a modern computer with standard software. The essence of this program is that distance education and modern techniques and technology are inseparable from each other. Today, a student can study almost all Western university programs without leaving his country. Education is becoming universal and universally used ahead of the processes of political and economic unification. Distance education differs from traditional forms of education by the following characteristics:

- **Adaptability.** The ability to work out when you want, where you want, and at your own pace. There is no limit to the time allocated to mastering science.
- **Modularity.** Formation of study plans that meet individual or group needs from independent subject courses-modules.
- **Parallelism.** Education in parallel with professional activity or studies at other educational institutions.
- **Social equality.** Equality of access to education, regardless of where the student lives, health status, and financial means.

The quality of distance education as a full-time form of education does not depend on the involvement of outstanding teaching staff and the use of the best teaching-methodical works and subject control tests in the educational process. They include a set of all pedagogical acts in the relationship between the teacher and students. Distance learning uses innovative, computer-based, telecommunications-based, and the latest advances in educational technology along with traditional teaching tools.

Most of the educational scientific materials form a virtual-informational, educational environment due to the remoteness of the audience. Electronic publications intended for the

educational process, having all the features of paper publications, have several aspects and advantages. In particular, it is a computer memory or disk compact storage, hypertext capabilities, the ability to increase, the ability to quickly make changes and additions, the convenience of sending information by e-mail, an automated learning system, which includes didactic, methodological and informational materials and software for the study program. In addition, it allows them to be used comprehensively in independent learning and control. Distance learning method has the following advantages:

a) creative environment of teaching. Based on many existing methods, the teacher gives knowledge, and the student only reads the given material. On the basis of the proposed distance education, the students themselves search for the necessary information from the information bank on the basis of computers, and of course share their experiences with others on the basis of electronic networks. This ensures that students communicate well with others and encourages such work-based learning.

b) the possibility of independent education. Education based on the distance method includes the stages of primary, secondary, university, correspondence - evening and advanced training. Inspectors of varying levels of preparation can work around their own timetables and interact with students at their own level.

c) major changes in the workplace. The type of education based on the distance method creates comfortable conditions for millions of people, especially for those who receive education without being separated from production. Teaching based on this method plays a very big role in the training of personnel, that is, it is possible to get knowledge at the place of work without geographical and financial difficulties.

d) a new and effective means of teaching and learning. Statistics show that distance education is as effective as study without separation from production.

In addition, distance education goes beyond the limits set by the university. The advantage of the students or students who are studying on such a basis is that they are provided with the best, quality materials and teachers. It is determined based on the performance of mastering tasks and tests. The faster the trainees and students master the given task, the faster they will complete the course and study and receive a certificate. If he cannot master the program, he will be given the opportunity to work independently and continue his studies. Distance learning also has organizational economic advantages. Auditoriums and dormitories are not necessary for distance learning.

Conclusion: It can be said as a conclusion to the opinions expressed at the top that the main goal of using innovative pedagogical technologies in educational processes is to achieve the commonality of teacher and student, to further strengthen the interest of students in science, to change their attitude to education, to form the ability of students to apply the learned and accumulated knowledge in social conditions in appropriate situations, to combine information and communication technologies and didactic materials with any subject of science. It should be emphasized that innovative pedagogical technologies are important in the educational process in training modern specialists who will be in demand in the labor market in the future. If innovative technologies are considered as a driving force of educational development, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in education will undoubtedly serve only for the benefit. The future of every society, the level of development of the educational system, which is considered an integral

part and a vital necessity, is determined not only by the development, but also by the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies in educational processes.

REFERENCES:

1. Abduraximova Dilora Karimovna. (2023). THE NEED TO INTRODUCE FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE BANKING SERVICES MARKET. Academia Science Repository, 4(05), 54–62. Retrieved from <http://academiascience.com/index.php/repo/article/view/439>
2. Alavutdinova, N., & Ergasheva, L. (2024). COMMUNICATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Science and innovation, 3(B1), 29-34.
3. Karimovna, A. D. (2023). BANK INNOVATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE ECONOMY. Open Access Repository, 10(11), 44-50.
4. Мамбетова, Г. Ж. (2016). Семантика некоторых гидронимических индикаторов в каракалпакском языке. International scientific journal, 65.
5. Jubatkhonovna, S. S., & Jaksimuratovna, M. G. (2021). Types of structure of phraseologies in the work of T. Kaipbergenov “The secret known only to you”. Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT), 12(14), 4486-4490.
6. Saodat, S. (2023). Study of Somatic Phraseological Units in Karakalpak Language.
7. Jubatkhonova, S. S. (2023). RELATIONSHIP OF LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN LINGUOCULTUROLOGY. Miasto Przyszłości, 35, 238-243.